

Magnetic and Infrared Studies of Metal Complexes of Quinoline-2-aldehyde Thiosemicarbazone

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Solid complexes of quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (QAT) with copper (II), nickel (II), cobalt (III), palladium (II), zinc (II) and cadmium (II) have been prepared and characterized by uv and ir techniques. Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes are also measured. The results suggest the formation of 5-membered chelates involving chelation through hydrazinic nitrogen and thioenolic sulphur.

IN view of antituberculosis¹ and other pharmacological²⁻⁷ activities of metal thiosemicarbazides in biological systems, the physicochemical studies of the metal complexes are desired. Quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (QAT) has been used in this laboratory for spectrophotometric determination of palladium, nickel, copper and iron⁸⁻⁹. This communication describes the isolation and characterization of some metal complexes with QAT.

Experimental

Preparations :

Quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (QAT) : This ligand was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantity of quinoline-2-aldehyde and thiosemicarbazide in minimum amount of ethanol for 3 hrs. The white needle-shaped crystals were collected, washed with distilled water, ether and finally with ethanol; m.p. 234°. Solution of QAT in DMF-H₂O (1:1) was employed for preparation of metal complexes.

Metal Complexes :

a) **Bis (quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazonato) copper(II) :** The copper complex was obtained by mixing acidic solution of cupric chloride (0.34 g in 100 ml) and ligand solution (0.92 g in 100 ml) in 1:2 molar ratio and dropwise addition of sodium hydroxide solution (1 M) till the chocolate colour complex precipitated out (pH 7 to 8). The complex was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and dried under vacuum. Yield 1.2 g.

b) **Pyridine and picoline adduct of bis (quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazonato) nickel(II) :** The ethanolic solution of brown coloured nickel(II) complex, obtained by mixing acidic solution of nickel chloride (0.28 g in 100 ml) and ligand solution (0.46 g in 100 ml) in 1:2 molar ratio and dropwise addition of 1 M sodium hydroxide (pH 7.5 to 8), was refluxed for 2 hrs over a water bath with either pyridine or β -picoline in 1:2 molar ratio. On keeping the reaction mixture overnight dark brown solids separated out. The adducts were filtered, washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum. Yield 1.2 g.

c) **Bis (quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazonato) palladium(II) :** The palladium complex was prepared by mixing acidic solution of palladium chloride (0.17g in 100 ml) and ligand solution (0.46 g in 100 ml) in 1:2 molar ratio and dropwise addition of 1 M sodium acetate solution (pH 1 to 2) till the orange red complex precipitated out. The filtered precipitate was washed with water, ethanol and dried under vacuum. Yield 2.0 g.

d) **Tris (quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazonato) cobalt(III) :** The cobalt complex was prepared by mixing aqueous solution of CoCl₂·6H₂O (0.23 g in 100 ml) and ligand solution (0.69 g in 100 ml) in 1:3 molar ratio and adding 1 M sodium hydroxide solution till dark brown complex separated out (pH 7 to 8). The complex was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and dried under vacuum. Yield 1.1 g.

e) **Bis (quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazonato) zinc(II) and cadmium(II) :** Zinc and cadmium complexes were obtained by mixing acidic solution of zinc sulphate (0.28 g in 100 ml) and cadmium nitrate (0.30 g in 100 ml) with ligand solution (0.46 g in 100 ml) in 1:2 molar ratio and dropwise addition of 1 M sodium hydroxide till the complexes precipitated out (pH 6.5 to 7.8). The yellow complexes were filtered, washed with water, ethanol and dried under vacuum. Yield of zinc and cadmium complexes were 1.3 g and 1.1 g respectively.

Physical measurements : Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at room temperature by Guoy method using mercury tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) as calibrant. Infrared spectra in the range 4000-700 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 221 IR spectrometer, in nujol mull. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 37 UV-vis spectrophotometer. Metal estimations were carried out by standard methods^{10,11} whereas nitrogen and sulphur were estimated by micro-analytical methods. Molecular weights of the complexes were determined by cryoscopy.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic and analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. Elemental analysis and

TABLE 1—MAGNETIC AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF QAT

Compound	Colour	Decomp temp °C	M%	Found N%	S%	M%	Calculated N%	S%	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
Cu(QAT) ₂	Chocolate	282	11.85	21.4	12.1	12.1	21.5	12.2	1.94
Ni(QAT) ₂ . 2Py	Dark brown	260	8.2	21.0	9.2	8.2	20.7	9.4	3.14
Ni(QAT) ₂ . 2Pic	Dark brown	286	8.2	20.0	9.8	8.3	19.4	10.0	3.19
Pd(QAT) ₂	Orange red	252	18.9	19.5	11.2	19.0	19.8	11.3	Dimag
Co(QAT) ₂	Dark brown	272	8.0	12.2	8.9	8.0	12.8	8.6	Dimag
Zn(QAT) ₂	Yellow	293	12.6	20.5	12.1	12.5	21.2	12.2	Dimag
Cd(QAT) ₂	Yellow	292	19.4	19.5	11.0	19.6	19.6	11.2	Dimag

molecular weight determinations of the complexes indicate 1:2 stoichiometry for copper, palladium, zinc and cadmium complexes. Cobalt, however, forms CoL₃ type complex. The pyridine and picoline adducts of Ni(II)-QAT complexes are also found to contain molecules of bases thus corresponding to Ni(QAT)₂. 2Py and Ni(QAT)₂. 2Pic formulae. The magnetic moments of *bis* (quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazonato) copper(II) at room temperature was found to be 1.94 B.M. The value is slightly higher than that expected for metal ion containing one unpaired electron. This difference in magnetic moments is attributed to orbital contribution. Though three transition $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2A_{1g}$, $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2B_{2g}$ and $2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ are expected for copper(II) complexes, they are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band. The electronic spectra of four coordinated copper complexes show one broad band in the range 430 to 450 nm thus suggesting square planar geometry. The tetrahedral complex shows no d-d absorption band¹³.

The magnetic moments of Ni(QAT)₂. 2 Py and Ni(QAT)₂. 2 Pic were found to be 3.14 and 3.19 B.M. respectively and these values are consistent with the generally accepted values for high spin octahedral complexes involving SP³d² bond hybridization. The electronic spectrum of the nickel adducts show an absorption band at 31.9 kK which may be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The band at 27.0 kK is attributed to charge transfer transition whereas the d-d absorption band is seen at 20.9 kK. These transition in Ni(QAT)₂. 2Py and Ni(QAT)₂. 2Pic indicates an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

All other complexes were found to be dimagnetic. This reveals that the palladium complex must be

planar in structure whereas cobalt complex is octahedral involving d²SP³ hybridization. Cobalt(II) thus gets oxidized to cobalt(III) during complexation. A band at 400 nm (25 kK) in the uv spectra of palladium complex has been assigned to $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1B_{1g}$ transition. This suggests the square planar geometry of palladium-QAT complex. The band at 28.25 kK may be assigned to $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1E_g$ transition¹⁸. The electronic spectrum of the cobalt(III) complex has two d-d bands at 24.5 kK and 22 kK due to $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{1g}$ and $1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1T_{2g}$ transitions as expected for a spin paired octahedral complex¹⁴. Zinc(II) and cadmium(II) complexes are generally tetrahedral.

An assignment of the important ir absorption bands is based on the study of ir of the free ligand and their chelates and the same is reported in Table 2. The ligand exhibits three bands in the region 3390-3140 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to NH and NH₂ stretching. The intensity of these bands is considerably lowered in metal complexes. Moreover, the bands are broad and the number of bands decreases in this region. All these observations are attributed to the fact that the hydrazine nitrogen of the system -CH=N-NH-CS-NH₂ participates in the chelate formation. The band at about 1610 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand which has been assigned to NH₂ deformation¹⁵ is sufficiently changed in the metal complexes. The strong band at 1525 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the ligand due to -CH=N shifts to 1575-1590 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes. This further suggests the coordination of the ligand to the metal through nitrogen atom of -CH=N. The strong band at 1610 cm⁻¹ in the ligand may also be assigned to C=N stretching¹⁶ and the same band either disappears or appears at lower frequency in metal complexes. $\nu(\text{CN}) + \nu(\text{NH}_2)$ vibration frequency has been observed at 1500 cm⁻¹ in the

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR ABSORPTION BANDS OF QAT AND THEIR METAL COMPLEXES

QAT	Cu(QAT) ₂	Ni(QAT) ₂ . 2py	Ni(QAT) ₂ . 2pic	Pd(QAT) ₂	Co(QAT) ₂	Zn(QAT) ₂	Cd(QAT) ₂	Assignment
3390 s	3400 b,w			3390 b,w		3350 m		NH and
3250 m		3275 b,m	3260 b,m			3290 m	3290 s	
3140 s	3120 b,w	3120 sh		3120 b	3140 sh	3150 m	3140 m	NH ₂ stret
2850 s	2860 m	2850 m	2840 m	2850 m	2850 w	2860 s	2860 m	
1610 s	1630 m	1620 sh	1620 sh	1630 s	1620 sh	1640 s	1660 s	=CH stret
—	—	1590 s	1590 s	—	—	1610 m	1590 m	
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	δNH ₂ or C=N
1525 s	1575 m	1570 s	1570 s	1580 m	1590 w	1580 m	1570 s	
1500 m	1525 w	1530 s	1530 s	—	1510 w	1530 m	1530 w	CH=N
1110 s	1160 m	1140 s	1130 s	1140 s	1160 m	1160 m	1140 s	
—	1110 b	1110 s	1110 s	1120 s	1120 s	1120 s	1110 s	νCN + νNH ₂
1320 m	—	1310 w	1300 w	1290 w	—	1320 s	—	
830 b,w	810 b,w	—	820 b,w	—	—	820 m	825 b	(CN) + (N-N)
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	C=S
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	stret

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, b = broad, sh = shoulder

free ligand but this band shifts to higher frequency (1530-1525 cm^{-1}) in metal complexes. The bands appearing around 1320 and 830 cm^{-1} in the ligands may be assigned to C=S stretching vibrations. In the metal complexes these bands are weakened and lowered. In some complexes these bands disappear. These observations indicate the coordination of the ligand through sulphur atom. Thus it can be concluded that the ligand QAT coordinates through hydrazinic nitrogen and thioenolic sulphur. The metal chelates therefore can be assigned the following tentative structure :

where M is either Cu(II), Ni(II), Pd(II), Co(III), Zn(II) or Cd(II).

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